

THE MOST DISTRIBUTED TYPES OF HELMINTHS IN SURKHANDARYA AND THE WAYS OF INFECTION TO CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7494321>

ELSEVIER

Received: 22-12-2022

Accepted: 22-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

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Abstract... This article describes the most common types of helminths in Surkhandarya and the ways of infection in children and adolescents.

Keywords: Children, Laiamblya, Ostritsa. Helminths, helminths, helminths in children and adolescents, fauna of helminths, parasitic helminths in children and adolescents, worms, parasites, worms.

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НАИБОЛЕЕ РАСПРОСТРАНЕННЫЕ ВИДЫ ГЕЛЬМИНТОВ В СУРХАНДАРЬЕ И ПУТИ ЗАРАЖЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ И ПОДРОСТКОВ

SURXONDARYODA ENG KENG TARQALGAN GELMINTLAR TURLARI VA BOLALAR VA O'SMIRLARGA YUQISH YO'LLARI

Received: 22-12-2022

Accepted: 22-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

Abstract... В данной статье описаны наиболее распространенные виды гельминтов в Сурхандарьинской области и пути заражения детей и подростков..

Keywords: Дети, Лаямбля, Острица. Гельминты, гельминтозы, гельминтозы у детей и подростков, фауна гельминтов, паразитарные гельминты у детей и подростков, глисты, паразиты, глисты..

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Currently, the majority of helminths cause infectious diseases. Infectiousness of helminths is an urgent problem. Helminthiasis occurs as a result of the entry of parasitic worms into the human body. To date, about 250 types of such pests have been identified, 9 of which were found in children. If a child has the following symptoms, he may have one of these parasites: abdominal pain; loss of appetite; The child is nervous; A child grinds his teeth in a dream. The parasite leaves the human body from 5 to 150 thousand pieces. Their danger is that they develop quickly and spread through the intestines through internal organs and systems. Doctors say that parasites can be transmitted in different ways depending on the type. For example, roundworms are mostly found in children who do not wash their hands well. Ostriches can be transmitted to humans through dirty hands, food, and dust that enters the mouth and nose.

Disease symptoms: Depending on the type and number of worms and in which organ they parasitize, the disease progresses differently. A person infected with parasites loses weight, has abdominal pain, nausea, diarrhea, or dizziness, says Saodat Temirova, a doctor of infectious diseases who spoke with us. If the worm is in the intestine - constipation or diarrhea, nausea and vomiting are observed. If it is in the liver - the whites of the eyes and the body will turn yellow, swelling will appear, various spots may appear on the body. If it is in the lungs - fever and cough may appear. Also, a person's ability to work decreases, children's development lags behind, they do not grow well, memory decreases, sleep becomes restless. The classification of helminths is very wide, especially in countries with a warm climate. Currently, we will focus only on those helminths that are widespread in our region.

Among them, one of the common species in Surkhandarya is LYaMBLYa. Currently, the most common type of parasite is giardia. Laiamblia is a simple, simple animal. It grows by itself in the human body. According to doctor Saodat Temirova's personal experience, it is appropriate to treat giardiasis only if there is a complaint. Symptoms of Lyamlblya include loss of appetite, difficulty eating breakfast in the morning, walking on an empty stomach all day, whimsical behavior in children, diarrhea, and constipation.

White spots on the face are not always a sign of worms. They can also be caused by a fungus. Giardia is often treated with an enema, but it is useless to do an enema when it is lost. Because the enema does not reach the place where giardia is located. Giardia is more parasitic in the bile ducts and duodenum. When we eat

food, it passes from the stomach to the duodenum for digestion. Giardia is fed with vitamins, minerals, potassium, calcium necessary for a person of twelve fingers. Giardia can be transmitted from unboiled water and drinks. One of the ways to treat giardia is to drink a medicine that kills it for 5 days. But before giving this medicine, the liver should be thoroughly checked. Then the dead giardia should be soaked for 5 days. If 20 days or 1 month of grass driver (corn cob) is given, giardia will die. Lyamblyya does not need to be treated lying down, said our doctor Saodat Temirova, who shared his advice and recommendations.

Another type is OYSTER. The most common parasite in children is ostriches (a roundworm), which causes enteribiosis. These helminths are small, about 1 cm in size, white-gray in color, and have a curved body.

The location of these parasites is the large intestine, sometimes they can also be located in the lower part of the small intestine. Ostrich reproduction takes place around the skin of the anus. At night, the female ostrich goes to the folds of the skin to lay her eggs, and in girls, it often goes to the labia. These helminths live for 1-1.5 months. A child's self-harm can cause him to be restless for years. The parasite can be seen with the naked eye in feces. If the ostrich gets into the stomach and intestines, it means that the body is infected with parasites. Ostrich eggs fall into the environment with contaminated feces. The outer shell of eggs is resistant to unfavorable environment and its size is very small. In order to learn about the environment, to know the taste and composition of objects, the child takes everything with his hands and takes them to his mouth. In this way, the eggs of the ostrich enter the organism of its "future little master". An oyster is from 20 cm to 40 cm. Lives for 21 days. The easiest way to treat oysters is to pay attention to cleanliness.

Helminths are known to live in their hosts, feed on them, and defend themselves. They are able to accommodate both people and animals. They are usually disease generators and can weaken the affected body over time. As an object of clinical research, helminthology in medical services determined the classification of helminths according to their external forms and the organs in which they are located. They are also supported by data related to their juvenile, egg, and developmental stages from larva to adult. Currently, there are three classifications for this animal group: cestodes, trematodes and nematodes. Helminths as a group are able to live in the intestines, blood and urinary tract. Depending on the residence, the accommodation is different.²²¹

ASKARIDA is another type that is common among children and teenagers in Surkhandarya. Another common type of parasite that is common in children is roundworm. The size of these nematodes reaches 15 cm. The parasite settles in the small intestine and eats the falling food. Ascaris rarely falls into the feces. Eggs can be found in the analysis of feces of a female soldier. If eggs are not found in the stool analysis, this does not mean that the child is not infected with ascarida. The life cycle of Ascarida can reach several years. Since the child's body has a low ability to fight, the parasite can multiply easily. Worms can also be infected through unwashed fruit and contaminated water. Often, contamination can be observed when children interact with animals, when they play in the soil and sand with their litter. Children do not wash their hands after playing on the street, parasites enter the body at this time. Therefore, all children can be affected equally, regardless of living conditions and upbringing environment.

Detection methods After the child is infected and when the first symptoms appear, the following measures must be taken if parasites are suspected:

- Stool analysis is taken 3 times, the interval should be several days;

²²¹ S.D. DADAYEV, G.A. ABDURAKHANOVA "GENERAL PARASITOLOGY" by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan 5A 140101 - Study guide for students majoring in biology (by science) TASHKENT-2012 page 13

- Blood analysis for helminths;
- General analysis of blood (to ostrich eggs);

As an additional check:

- UTT of internal members;
- X-ray;
- CT and MRT;

These tests reveal the locations of parasites in other organs. It should be noted that the disease is individual in each person, taking into account that, you should not forget to consult a doctor before taking any treatment. Parasites will not bother you and your children if you make time for your children twice a year, consult a doctor and check them, and most importantly pay attention to hygiene and cleanliness. It is also important to note that if one person in the family is infected with this disease, all family members must be treated with strict hygiene. Because it is very fast multiplying and fast spreading.

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